

POLITICAL TEXT AS A SPECIFIC EXPRESSION OF THE POLITICAL LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article gives valuable data on Political text as a specific expression of the political language. And there is also information about the functions of political terminology.

Key words: persuasive speech, structure arguments, sales pitches, body language, logical appeals, art of argument, propaganda

The nature of political language technology can be specifically defined by examining the elements that make up a political text. The scope of a political text can include persuasive writing, deceit, or even hugging, all of which call for a particular kind of attention - usage of language. The goal of a persuasive speech is to persuade the audience to agree with a viewpoint or idea that the speaker presents. If the speaker can effectively structure the arguments as a solution to a problem, then this will be accomplished. The audience must first be persuaded that the speaker or writer is important to them, and then they must be persuaded by the text that the speaker or writer has the solution for solving the problem. Persuasive speeches can take many different forms, including debates, political processes, and sales pitches. Persuasive speeches can make use of factors like body language and emotional and/or logical appeals. The effectiveness of a persuasive speech is influenced by the audience's willingness to listen as well as the setting in which it is delivered.

A successful persuasion requires an art of argument. A logical argument in politics is known as a "political argument." Academics, the media, and candidates for political office and government positions all use political arguments. They could also be employed by citizens in regular interactions to discuss and comprehend political developments. Political arguments frequently repeat the same premises and facts in slightly different ways, making them circular. Propaganda differs from argumentation in that the former has minimal structural or rationality.

A specific type of argument is one that is based on probability and is based on an observational experience finding that the majority considers acceptable and true, perhaps the most persuasive arguments are those that include facts, statistics, research findings, summaries of reports, or references to relevant literature. (Zemplén-Kutrovatz 2012)

If persuasion based on argument does not achieve success, then deceit, misguidance and hustling follow. This means that in order to achieve their aim, the speakers present false data, show bogus statistics and make promises that cannot be kept due to objective circumstances. Politics is saturated with speeches: citizens and politicians speak, journalists and political analysts give speeches and, last but not least, political scientists speak as well (Cacioppo and Petty 1986)

It is true that different readings of political writings lead to various interpretations, which give the text fresh relevance and meaning, but the most crucial question still needs to be answered: what does the text mean? What do they have to say to us? One needs to be well-versed in political language in order to respond to this question.

Professional language is how the political science discourse is presented. Political speech, however, cannot be understood in a vacuum from other but closely related political

discourses. When an initial notion of the function of language in politics is developed, and when language also becomes a pertinent issue from a political standpoint, issues pertaining to the linguistic aspects of politics arise.

Political terminology has the following functions:

- expressive function, meaning that it expresses aims that are rooted in the real sphere of politics
- objective function, meaning that it has an objective reason to influence people's thinking, feelings, and thus their actions;
- symbolic function, meaning that thoughts and feelings are expressed by political symbols.

According to the symbolic approach, if someone is talking about symbolic politics, then (s)he refers to an individual area of politics that is genuine and separate from real and actual political issues. In habitual language use, symbolic politics means a publicly displayed deception or surrogate action that is used to detract from actual political reality. In this sense symbolic politics is considered to be a surrogate for politics. Symbolic politics differs from substantial policy. As a policy of signs (terms and slogans, badges, banners and pictures, gestures, ritual acts, and political staging), symbolic politics evolves in a semantic field. Substantial policy, by contrast, consists of a revisable succession of political decisions (e.g., legislation, contracts, taxes, etc.). Symbolic politics and substantial policy can be related to each other. On the one hand, symbolic politics can have an impact on substantial policy, while substantial policy can be communicated, implemented, or averted by symbolic politics (Sarcinelli 1998). If we try to define political jargon from the perspective of language policy, we notice that this conception of language directs attention to the concept of fighting.

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